

Full Length Article

Advanced catalyst layers for PEM fuel cell produced by inkjet printing: Catalyst layer optimisation and comparison with ultrasonic-spray-coated one

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ABSTRACT

Industrial inkjet printing (IJP) emerges as a progressive technology for scalable and precise deposition of catalyst layers (CLs) in proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs). In this study, an industrial piezo-IJP head was used for deposition of the CLs directly onto a Nafion™ 212 membrane. Several strategies to mitigate cracks in CLs were considered: addition of ethylene glycol to the inkjet ink, adjusting distance between the printhead and the membrane, and reducing printing resolution in combination with specific algorithms of the drops order. The optimised printing parameters were used to fabricate crack free homogenous catalyst coated membranes (CCMs) with Pt loadings on the cathode varying from 0.1 to 0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻². During operation in a PEMFC, IJP layers showed superior performance to CCMs produced by ultrasonic spray coating (USC). The USC CCMs reached a peak power density of 1.12 W cm⁻² with 0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² on the cathode, while the IJP reached a peak power density of 1.13 W cm⁻² already with 0.1 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² on the cathode. This enhancement was attributed to the reduced ohmic resistance and increased Pt utilisation, achieved through optimisation of the catalyst layer transport properties. These findings highlight the potential of IJP for high-capacity production of low loaded CLs with improved performance.

1. Introduction

Proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) represent a key technology for the transition to clean energy with minimal carbon dioxide footprint. Combining high energy conversion efficiency and compact modular design, they are suitable for a wide range of applications, from stationary devices to transportation [1–4]. PEMFC performance is highly dependent on the quality of catalyst layers (CLs), which facilitate the electrochemical reactions by providing sites where the gas, ionic, and electronic phases intersect in a three-phase boundary [1–4]. The deposition technique chosen for the fabrication of catalyst-coated membranes (CCMs) plays a crucial role in determining the structural and functional properties of the resulting CLs [1,5,6].

Advanced methods that allow precise control over the structure and composition of CCMs are essential, particularly with respect to economic considerations such as scalability and waste reduction [7–11]. Large-scale manufacturing methods are usually abbreviated as roll-to-roll

(R2R) methods. Among these, the most associated techniques are slot-die coating, ultrasonic spray coating (USC), gravure printing, screen-printing, among which slot-die coating is the most promising one [8,11].

USC employs high-frequency sound waves to generate fine ink droplets, which are deposited onto the membrane surface using a focussing gas. USC is frequently used not only in the laboratory but also on an industrial scale, because it supports a broad range of inks and is efficient in catalyst dispersion, leading to high Pt utilisation. Nevertheless, it may suffer from drawbacks, such as ink loss at the mask edges and variations in the layer thickness [5]. Despite these facts, USC has shown promise in fabricating high-performance CCMs with reduced platinum loadings [5–8].

Inkjet printing (IJP) utilizes the piezo effect to generate tiny picolitre sized drops of uniform volume. This is a well-established and widely used technique in the graphical industry. Because IJP is additive and digitally controlled, it is also utilised in printed electronics, e.g., for producing sensors, transistors, photodetectors, conductive elements.

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Fig. 1. Deposition methods used for the CCM production: piezo inkjet printing (IJP) and ultrasonic spray coating (USC).

Using piezoelectric actuators to dispense catalyst ink, IJP allows precise control of thickness and morphology, as well as Pt loading [5–18]. This technique is also suitable for deposition of material gradients in CLs, potentially improving electrochemical efficiency of cells [19–22]. At the same time, drop-on-demand (DoD) piezo-inkjet printing is probably the most demanding technology in terms of ink formulation. The width of the nozzle in inkjet is typically tens of microns, therefore, the size of the particles should be in a submicrometric range to prevent clogging. Agglomerates within the ink and ink sedimentation are critical for the stable jetting and reproducibility of the printing results as well. Also, the viscosity should fall into a very narrow range typically below 20 mPa s, which may force to the use of low concentrated inks. However, with the proper ink formulation, inkjet printing becomes a powerful tool for fabricating customised CLs in a variety of shapes and gradients of catalyst and ionomer. In addition, IJP, due to its digital nature, is associated with low-waste production and is well suited for electrodes with ultra-low Pt loading. Finally, lab-scale IJP, which is currently reported in the scientific literature for catalyst deposition, is scalable to high-speed production by integration of industrial printheads in a R2R environment.

Numerous studies preferred lab-scale piezo inkjet printer from Dimatix Materials Printer for CLs deposition due to its open architecture and the ability to control waveform and other printing parameters [11,12,15,18,19,22]. The inkjet heads used for catalyst deposition have only 16 nozzles with 10 pl drop volume, arranged in a row with a width of less than 4 mm. The actual print width is even narrower due to the need to tilt the printhead for the desired drop spacing. Large catalyst areas must be printed line by line. According to our previous experience [18], production time of one CCM with a catalyst area of 5 cm x 5 cm ranges from tens of minutes to several hours, depending on the desired Pt loading and ink formulation. The industrial printhead used in this paper has 256 nozzles with a nominal drop volume of 80 pl each, arranged in a row of 64 mm. This is an order of magnitude change in the printing scale compared to the laboratory-scale print heads.

High-capacity printing means that a large amount of solvent is applied to the membrane in a short period of time, which causes its swelling and development of cracks in catalyst layers. The industrial printhead applies ink across the entire width of the sample, making it even more difficult to mitigate the cracks. Recently, an industrial printhead was utilised to produce CCMs on Gore membrane [23]. The authors highlighted the problem of the catalyst inhomogeneity and crack formation caused by material flow and high solvent content in the ink and suggested reducing the drop volume and resolution of the printing. Fluctuations in Pt loading relative to the printing direction

were also detected for the lab-scale printheads [18]. In this paper, we considered several strategies for cracks mitigation and improving layer homogeneity: varied resolution in combination with the number of printed layers, a specific algorithm of the drop order, as well as the varied distance between membrane and printhead.

Finally, also the ink formulation seems to play crucial role in cracks formation. Solvents with a high boiling point can be used in the inkjet ink formulation as a humectant. Such additives influence the formation of the printed layer on the microstructure level. For example, the addition of propylene glycol (PG) to the catalyst ink was found to inhibit crack formation in CLs during drying processes [24]. Similar observations were made for other glycol-based additives that served for lower ionomer aggregates, thinner ionomer layers around the catalyst, and crack-free CLs [25,26]. On this basis, two ink formulations with and without ethylene glycol (EG) were considered to produce inkjet catalyst layers.

It is clear that high-capacity production of PEMFCs is closely related to the necessity of versatile high-speed production technologies. At the same time, ensuring the lowest possible waste production is advisable, especially when using an expensive Pt catalyst. Accordingly, the aim of this study is to demonstrate the possibility of the transfer of the CL printing on a laboratory scale to an industrial print head without sacrificing the quality of the printed layers. Thus, proving the high potential of this additive technology to become a key player in the fuel cell technology of the future. The obtained results demonstrate the scaling issues, when large amounts of the ink are transferred directly onto the membrane, and presented mechanisms of their mitigation. Finally, the performance of the CCMs prepared by an optimised printing strategy was compared to that produced by USC in an operating laboratory-scale fuel cell.

2. Experimental

For comparison purposes, a standard ink composition was defined, suitable for both, inkjet printing and ultrasonic spray coating. This allows to determine the impact of the CL formation method without the need to consider the effect of a different ink formulation. Simplified diagrams of deposition techniques are shown in Fig. 1. Catalyst deposition according to the area of production is shown in Supplementary Information (SI): IJP (Fig. S1) and USC (Fig. S2).

One of the main differences between these two technologies is the way of ink transport to the membrane. In case of USC, an ultrasonication head with relatively wide nozzle creates the droplets mist, which is focused by inert gas flow. In contrast, IJP utilises piezo effect to generate

Table 1
Catalyst inks.

Ink	EG, wt.%	Solid content, wt. %	Density, g cm ⁻³	Kinematic viscosity, mm ² s ⁻¹	Dynamic viscosity, mPa·s
Ink A	0	2.4	0.89	4.6	4.1
Ink B	17.3	2.0	0.92	4.7	4.3

tiny picolitre sized drops of uniform volume along the whole nozzles row. Short videos of IJP (Video S1) and USC (Video S2) depositions are provided in SI.

2.1. Catalyst layer fabrication

2.1.1. Catalyst inks and membrane

Within the scope of this study, the ink had to be suitable for both, the IJP and USC deposition technique, both requiring contradicting compositions to a certain degree. In the case of IJP, a slow evaporation of solvents is desired to prevent nozzle clogging. In contrast, fast evaporation of solvents is preferred in the USC technique due to higher output flow rates. Both technologies typically use a mixture of alcohol and water for catalyst inks. A mixture of ethanol (boiling point 78 °C) and water was used as the basic ink composition. The final solvent ratio and solids content were determined in preliminary experiments based on the printability of the varied dispersions. The second ink was prepared with EG (boiling point 197 °C) to prevent catalyst crust on the nozzle plate.

Catalyst ink A was prepared by mixing 4.7 g of 5 wt% Nafion™ D521 dispersion in water:1-propanol (Chemours), 0.55 g of catalyst 29.1 wt% Pt/C TEC10V30E (Tanaka Kikinokoku) and 27.8 g of water:ethanol mixture (30:70 wt% ratio). Catalyst ink B contained additionally 6.9 g of ethylene glycol, which corresponds to 17.3 wt% in the ink. Ionomer to carbon weight ratio (I/C) was kept at a value of 0.6 for both inks.

Both mixtures, each with a volume of around 38 cm³ (ink A) and 45 cm³ (ink B), were sonicated in an ultrasonic bath (Ultrasonic Cleaner USC 300D, VWR) with a frequency of 45 kHz for 20 min and subsequently treated with an ultrasonic probe (Sonoplus HD 4100, Bandelin) for 10 min (pulse 0.5 s) to homogenize ink and break up agglomerates (power output: ~ 5.5 kJ). The density and kinematic viscosity of the inks were determined by using a pycnometer with a volume of 5 cm³ and an Ostwald viscosimeter. The ink characteristics are given in Table 1.

In described experiments, all inks were deposited directly on Nafion™ 212 membrane (Chemours).

2.1.2. Inkjet printing

For inkjet printing an industrial printhead Q-Class Sapphire QS-256/80 printhead (Fujifilm Dimatix) was chosen. The printhead is equipped with a silicon nozzle plate, which includes 256 independent piezo channels (nozzles) arranged in a row of 64.77 mm length. The native drop volume of each nozzle is 80 pl. Each nozzle has a square shape with the side length of approximate 46 μm (microscope measurement). The native resolution of the printhead is 100 dpi, and correspondingly the distance between the nozzles is 254 μm. The QS-printhead was driven by the PixDRO LP50 (SÜSS MicroTec SE). Details of the printing can be found in SI, including schematics in Fig. S1.

For a preliminary investigation on the influence of printing parameters on layer formation, small pieces of membrane were placed on a 1 mm thick glass slide, while the support film remained attached to the membrane. CLs with the size of 20 mm × 20 mm were printed with varied printing conditions: drop space, number of printed layers, and distance between printhead and membrane. The differences used in printing settings are described in the relevant chapters. The print direction with respect to the position of the sample were kept the same. The temperature of the printing table was set to 55 °C. The printing

speed was kept at 50.8 mm s⁻¹. Depending on the task, print resolutions in x and y direction were 1,000 dpi, 700 dpi, or 500 dpi, respectively. The distance between the printhead and printing table was set to 4 mm (if nothing else is specified). Printed samples were initially left on the printing table until the surface of the catalyst looked visibly dried to prevent spreading of the catalyst during transport to the oven. Then the samples were placed in the oven for a final drying at 80 °C for 30 min for the ink without EG and 100 °C for 2 h for the ink containing EG. In addition, CLs with varied Pt loadings were printed directly on a glass slide for further measurement of the layer thickness.

The CCMs (catalyst area 50 mm x 50 mm) for the electrochemical tests were prepared by inkjet printing of CLs directly onto the membrane using the ink A under optimised printing conditions (Tab. S1 in SI). Pt loading of the cathode side comprised 0.1 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², 0.2 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², and 0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻². Total Pt loading of the double sides printed CCMs comprised 0.2 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², 0.4 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², 0.6 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², respectively. Details on preparation can be found in SI.

2.1.3. Ultrasonic spray coating

The CLs were deposited using an in-house made system, consisting of an ultrasonication nozzle (capillary diameter of 750 μm) with integrated focusing N₂ gas delivery (50 cm³ min⁻¹) with a controller (Cheersonic), integrated into a x-y-z CNC platform (CZ Robotics). A linear movement of the nozzle was realised in a serpentine geometry with switching horizontal/vertical direction. This combination of two serpentine directions formed one deposited layer on a sample (Fig. S2 in SI). The deposition distance between the printed lines was 5 mm, the distance from the end of the nozzle to the membrane was 15 mm, and the movement speed was 4 m min⁻¹. The distance between the printed lines was set so that the spray pattern on the membrane overlapped. The ink was delivered to the nozzle by linear syringe pump (New Era Pumps) using 10 cm³ syringe and a flow of 0.3 cm³ min⁻¹. Both protective layers were removed from the membrane before deposition. The hotplate was set to 60 °C. Every deposited layer was left drying before the next layer deposition was commenced. The final Pt loading in the layers was estimated by calculation based on the volume of deposited ink and confirmed by weighting of sample before and after deposition. For selected representative samples, an exact determination of Pt loading was performed to validate this method. CL was dissolved in Aqua Regia, composed of 35 wt% HCl (Penta, per analysis) with 65 wt% HNO₃ (Penta, per analysis), at a temperature of 80 °C for 12 h under reflux cooler. After centrifugation, the sample solution was analysed on the ICP-OES analyser Optima 8000 (Perkin Elmer).

2.2. Characterization of the catalyst layers

The thickness of the CL was measured by stylus surface profiler Veeco Dektak 150 (Veeco Metrology) on a flat glass substrate. Microscopic images of CLs deposited on membrane were obtained by Axio Imager.M2.m microscope (Zeiss) in transmitted and reflected light. Additionally, images of CL samples on membrane were taken with backlight illumination to detect through-cracks formed along the whole area of the sample. The homogeneity of the catalyst distribution was examined by Micro-XRF spectrometer M4 Tornado (Bruker Nano GmbH) using spatially resolved fluorescence X-ray imaging. The obtained spectra were used for quantification of the total Pt loading of the sample using XMethod routine within M4 Tornado software. 2D maps of the Pt distribution were obtained for each sample separately and were not quantified for the 20 mm x 20 mm catalyst samples, therefore the maps indicate only the distribution of Pt within a specific sample. Pt maps for the 50 mm x 50 mm catalyst samples (IJP and USC) were quantified in QMap routine utilizing XMethod software suite. The complete area of each sample was scanned with a resolution of 150 μm. Quantification was done by binning 2 x 2 pixels.

Fig. 2. A) Drop formation of ink A and a single dried drop onto membrane, B) drop formation of ink B and a single dried drop onto membrane, C) CL thickness measured on glass, D) CL formation for ink A, E) CL formation for ink B. Loading of the samples $0.15 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Print resolution 1000 dpi, 4 layers.

2.3. Single cell testing

Fuel cell performance was evaluated in a $5 \text{ cm} \times 5 \text{ cm}$ AirCell LT (LeanCat) single-cell operated at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with fully humidified gases. The MEA was assembled directly in the cell without hot-pressing, using Sigracet 22BB gas-diffusion layers and a pneumatic clamping pressure of 5 bar to ensure uniform compression. Hydrogen and oxygen were supplied under 0.5 bar overpressure with stoichiometric ratios of 1.5 (H_2) and 3 (O_2).

Cells underwent a standard break-in procedure at 1 A cm^{-2} before recording polarisation curves and electrochemical impedance spectra (EIS) using a Solartron ModuLab XM system. The EIS was measured between 10 kHz and 0.1 Hz at set current densities ranging from 0.2 to 1.5 A cm^{-2} and analysed using an equivalent-circuit model composed of 3–4 Voigt elements. Electrochemical surface area (ECSA) was determined from cyclic voltammetry under N_2/H_2 with 100 ml min^{-1} flowrate.

All experimental details, instrument parameters, cell-assembly steps, data-fitting procedures, and representative circuit diagrams are provided in the SI (Section 1.3, Figs. S3 and S4).

3. Results and discussion

Development of an IJP CLs consists of three closely interconnected steps: (i) ink formulation, (ii) optimisation of the printing parameters, and (iii) determination of CL performance. In the following text, the individual steps will be discussed in more details.

3.1. Validation of the formulated inks

Ink A without EG and ink B with EG (Table 1) were used for inkjet printing. Both inks tended to form satellite droplets (Fig. 2A, B). In spite

of this, the main drop and satellite were forming a single circle spot on a membrane. Drops generated by ink A (Fig. 2A, inlay) demonstrate coffee ring effect with collecting the catalyst at the edge, while catalyst in ink B (Fig. 2B, inlay) accumulates in the centre of the drop, which can be explained by the presence of EG till the end of the drying process. Ink A formed a dried catalyst film on the nozzle plate due to increased print-head temperature (up to $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) during travel over the heated printing table, which caused fast evaporation of the ethanol–water mixture. To prevent nozzle clogging, the printhead was frequently wiped. In contrast, ink B with high boiling point solvent EG required less cleaning cycles and had a better latency, which means that the printhead started without any issues after the idle run.

The Pt maps of ink B CLs indicate redistribution of catalyst towards the right edge (Fig. 2E). This did not occur with ink A due to the faster drying of the ethanol–water mixture almost upon contact with the membrane.

The CL made from ink B had minor cracks optically. Cracks developed more intensely in areas with higher Pt concentration, coinciding with an increase in CL thickness (Fig. 2E). In contrast, the CL sample printed with ink A had significantly more cracks on the whole printed area (Fig. 2D). In the middle of the sample, cracks developed in a net, which can be attributed to accumulation of catalyst in this position according to the Pt map distribution and a slower drying rate in comparison to the edges. Sample A also demonstrated the alignment of the cracks in the printing direction. At the same time, the cracks in sample B were more randomly arranged.

A difference in the thickness of the CLs printed on glass between the two types of the catalyst inks emerges at higher loadings (Fig. 2C). While EG can still evaporate from very thin layers, it becomes trapped in the CLs with higher ink quantity.

Although the presence of EG in the ink was beneficial for the inkjet ink printability and crack mitigation, it may lead to an inhomogeneity of

Fig. 3. CLs printed on membranes (upper row) and corresponding microscopic images of the catalyst layers in relation to distance (h) between the printhead and the membrane. Print resolution 1000 dpi, 4 layers. RL – reflective light. TL – transmitted light.

the Pt distribution, possible entrapment of EG in the CL, and extension of the drying time. Finally, CCMs produced using ink B exhibited inferior performance, which can be attributed to the residuum of EG in the CL and membrane. Therefore, ink A without EG was used for the optimisation of layer quality in the next experiments.

3.2. Influence of the inkjet printing parameters on the catalyst layer formation

3.2.1. Distance between printhead and membrane

In fact, the distance between the inkjet head and the printing table significantly influences the printing quality. Generally, a shorter distance allows better control of the drop placement. In contrast, a longer distance can lead to blurring or edge distortion of the printed pattern. When it comes to the printing onto the membrane, the distance should be sufficient to prevent any collision of the printhead with the membrane if membrane swelling or wrinkling occurs. For the printing of the first side, in most cases, this was not an issue, since the membrane had a support film on the back side. When printing on the second side of the CCM, when the support had to be removed, the unsupported membrane was prone to swelling. The risk of collision between printhead and unsupported swelled membrane is increased, when the distance between printhead and membrane is below 4 mm, therefore $h = 4$ mm was considered as starting point for the experiments. A too short distance between the heated printing table and the inkjet head promoted drying of the ink on the nozzle plate.

The increase of the distance between the nozzle plate and the membrane led to a lower crack occurrence (Fig. 3). The heated printing table contributed to the temperature increase in the space between printhead and membrane. A longer flight distance to the substrate may result in a partial drying of the drops before they hit the membrane surface. This has both: pros and cons. Mist-like droplets contain less

solvent, which reduces excessive swelling of the membrane. At the same time, ink A tended to form satellite drops, which may result in a difference in the landing position of both parts of the drop when the distance to the membrane is increased. In addition, air movement under the printhead may change the trajectory of the drop. Both factors resulted in a more random drop deposition and CLs inaccuracy in comparison to the precisely landed ones when a short distance between the nozzle and the membrane was kept.

The shorter distance between membrane and printhead ($h \leq 16$ mm) is attributed to the excessive amount of the solvent which landed on the membrane surface. Due to the predominant volatile solvent in the catalyst ink, the drying process occurred relatively quickly, so the ink did not form a continuous wet film on the membrane, rather accumulated in the lines associated with the nozzle paths. The drying of such paths created material gradients that ultimately led to formation of cracks aligned in printing direction.

Although the larger distance between printhead and membrane was beneficial for crack mitigation, this also resulted in poorly defined borders of the CLs. The Pt map revealed an inhomogeneity of the catalyst distribution for the sample printed with $h = 24$ mm. This sample also had the lowest Pt loading of $0.09 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in comparison to $0.15 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for the sample printed at $h = 4$ mm, indicating deposition of the catalyst beyond the intended deposition area leading to catalyst losses. The first small loss of the catalyst was detected at $h = 16$ mm, where Pt loading comprises $0.14 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. In addition, sample printed with $h = 16$ mm still suffered from cracks and edge inaccuracy. The distance of 8 mm can be considered acceptable since at this point the edge of the catalyst layer is still defined, and only a small fraction of catalyst drops landed out of the intended area. Based on this investigation, the distance between the printhead and the membrane was set to 4 mm to prevent catalyst loss in the active area and maintain accurate edges.

Fig. 4. CLs on membrane printed with ink A at varied drop spaces and number of layers: A) 1,000 dpi, DS = 25.4 μm , 4 layers, B) 700 dpi, DS = 36.3 μm , 8 layers, C) 500 dpi, DS = 50.8 μm , 16 layers, D) 700 dpi with implemented algorithm of drops order, 8 layers. Loading of the samples $0.13 \pm 0.02 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Schematic: white circle – first order of drops, blue circle – second order of drops. RL – reflective light. TL – transmitted light. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.2.2. Drop spacing and sequence of the drop deposition

The drop spacing plays a key role in the crack formation. A significant reduction of cracks was observed when the drop spacing was increased while maintaining Pt loading through a higher number of overprints. Particularly, change from DS = 25.4 μm (1,000 dpi, 4 layers) to DS = 50.8 μm (500 dpi, 16 layers) resulted in an almost complete suppression of cracks in the CL (Fig. 4).

The effect of the drop spacing on crack mitigation can be related to the drop size. The volume of the drop generated by 1-pulse waveform at 70 V comprised $\sim 56 \text{ pl}$. Such drop formed a spot on the membrane surface with a diameter of 74 μm (Fig. 1A). Drops placed at closer distances collide with each other and form aligned material tracks in the printing direction. This cause local inhomogeneities, which later become a source of crack formation. If the density of the material in one layer is too high (DS = 25.4 μm) and the number of the layers is increasing, catalyst ink accumulated on top of membrane is causing its swelling and propagation of cracks in different directions (Fig. 4A).

As the distance between the drops increases (DS = 36.3 μm), drops organize in the narrower catalyst tracks. Cracks likely align in print direction in this case, because the low density of deposited material in each layer prevent accumulation of the wet ink (Fig. 4B). At a longer drop distance of 50.8 μm , drops still touch each other. However, the amount of deposited material in a printed layer is significantly reduced, which promotes the drying process of each individual drop almost on contact with the membrane, that reduces membrane swelling. Due to the low density of material in one overprint, multiple layers are required to maintain good coverage of the membrane. Thus, dividing the total ink volume into multiple overprints with lower drop density results in a reduction of cracks due to minimised swelling of the membrane.

Alternatively, a special algorithm that defines the order of drop deposition can be implemented to generate the high-resolution image on the membrane. The algorithm implies that only every second pixel in the line is printed with one nozzle (Fig. 4D). To maintain the necessary density of pixels, a second nozzle has to print additional tracks over previously printed tracks. In particular, at 700 dpi the drop space

between every second pixel is 72.6 μm , which almost matches the diameter of the dried drop. Splitting of the deposition steps prevent swelling of the membrane due to reduced amount of the material in each overprint and thus faster evaporation of the solvent. Compared to lower-resolution printing with higher number of printing layers, this deposition method improves membrane coverage due to better drop distribution across the membrane. This strategy was robust to crack mitigation for cathodes with varied Pt loading (0.1 – 0.3 $\text{mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), prepared for electrochemical tests.

Implementing the deposition algorithm to the ink B with EG resulted in improvement of the catalyst layer homogeneity. This happens due to reduced density of the material deposited in each layer, which supports fixing of the drops in the place of deposition and facilitates drying process. Corresponding pictures can be found in SI (Fig. S6).

The drop space regulated the amount of ink transferred to the unit area at a fixed time interval and at a constant speed of the printhead. When the drop space is similar to or larger than the drop diameter, than the drops are pinned almost at the point of landing. Ethanol, the more volatile solvent, evaporates first. Water, the less volatile component, remains in the ink longer. At this point, formation of a catalyst film is accompanied by a coffee ring effect and particles agglomeration. These effects are localised to the dimension of the drop or narrow line. At shorter drop space, wet nearby drops organise in larger wet tracks, followed by the broader solvent flow and agglomeration of catalyst particles during drying. Rapid and uneven drying resulted in differences in the surface stress across the CL, that led to crack formation. Depending on the amount of material transferred at one time, formation of long cracks aligned in print direction or a network of interconnected cracks can be expected to form. Implementation of the deposition algorithm resulted in complete crack suppression by dividing the total ink volume into smaller portions, that promotes gradual solvent removal in combination with homogeneous catalyst distribution.

The results obtained for ink A led to the conclusion that by accelerating the drying process, immediately after the drop hits the membrane, can reduce the occurrence of cracks. Therefore, further strategies can be

Fig. 5. Pt maps obtained by μ XRF: A) IJP $0.1 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, B) IJP $0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, C) USC $0.1 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, D) USC $0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ [to make the distribution better visible, the scale is limited to 0.49 while the max. value is 1.18].

considered:

- improved heat transfer from the printing table to the membrane, e.g., by the detachment of the support film from the membrane back side (Fig. S7B) at the cost of a risk of higher membrane mobility on the support and increased wrinkling during deposition,
- an extra drying time between the printing of the individual layers is beneficial for crack minimisation, but less feasible in terms of process intensification,
- change in printing direction by 90° to break the line structures caused by the sequential drop placement.

3.3. Physical characterization of printed CCMs

The homogeneity of the platinum distribution of the IJP and USC catalyst layers printed in a size of $5 \text{ cm} \times 5 \text{ cm}$ was assessed by micro-XRF for the cathodes with $0.1 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Fig. 5). IJP samples in general demonstrate homogenous Pt distribution across

the whole sample. Maximum Pt loading detected value for the samples of $0.1 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ comprises $0.17 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. According to Pt map distribution, the maximum values belong to high loaded spots (red pixels) isolated from each other. Such spots can be a result of catalyst agglomerates, formed during drying process, when the ratio of ethanol–water changed toward higher water content. They are well distributed across the whole area of the catalyst. As the number of printed layers increases to $0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the relative deviation decreases. The detected maximum value for the samples of $0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ comprises $0.4 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. USC samples have significantly higher deviation in Pt distribution. The detected maximum values for $0.1 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ comprise $0.28 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $1.18 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively. Catalyst distribution varies from the centre to the edges of the samples due to the deformation of the membrane during deposition.

Microscopic images of the cathode surfaces prepared by IJP and USC processes did not show the presence of cracks (Fig. S8). Microscale inhomogeneity was detected only for the low loaded UCS sample and with back light illumination. Cross section of IJP and USC layers obtained for

Fig. 6. A) Load curves, B) power curves of the tested CCMs, C) iR corrected load curves, D) peak power densities. Testing conditions: 80°C , O_2 and H_2 flow of 855 ml min^{-1} , 100 % relative humidity of the feed gases. The legend describes the deposition method and the cathodic Pt loading in the CCMs in $\text{mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (anode: cathode 1:1).

Fig. 7. A) Nyquist diagram at 1 A cm⁻², B) Ohmic and polarisation resistance, C) detailed polarisation resistance analysis. Operating conditions: 80 °C; O₂ and H₂ flow – 100 ml min⁻¹ at 0.2 A cm⁻², 143 ml min⁻¹ at 0.5 A cm⁻², 200 ml min⁻¹ at 0.7 A cm⁻², 285 ml min⁻¹ at 1.0 A cm⁻², 342 ml min⁻¹ at 1.2 A cm⁻², 427 ml min⁻¹ at 1.5 A cm⁻²; 100 % relative humidity of feed gases.

0.2 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² does not indicate significant difference in pore structure (Fig. S9). Both images reveal the typical granular morphology of aggregated catalyst layer structures. The layers seem to be in good contact with the underlying membrane. While these cross-sections provide qualitative insight into local compactness, interfacial contact, and general texture, SEM imaging inherently probes a very limited region of the electrode and cannot capture the macroscopic uniformity, thickness variation, or internal porosity distribution across the full active area. Moreover, the preparation of cross-sections can introduce local artifacts such as tearing or densification, meaning that apparent layer discontinuities or porosity features should be interpreted cautiously.

3.4. Electrochemical characterization

3.4.1. Load curves

As can be seen in Fig. 6, the performance of CCMs prepared via IJP and USC methods exhibits different trends with increasing cathode Pt loading. In the case of USC, performance improves steadily with higher loading, reaching a peak power density of approximately 1.12 W cm⁻² at 0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻². In contrast, IJP-based CCMs achieve their highest

performance already at the lowest loading of 0.1 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² and exhibit a gradual decline in performance with increasing loading. At 0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², the IJP CCM underperforms relative to its USC counterpart. This trend reversal suggests different rate-limiting processes dominating in each fabrication method.

The iR-corrected *I*-*U* curves in Fig. 6C confirm that ohmic losses alone do not account for these performance differences. Correction shifts the curves upward but does not alter the relative order or curvature, especially in the high current-density region. This indicates that activation and mass-transport losses are the dominant differences between the CLs. The voltage loss breakdown presented in Fig. S10 further illustrates this. Mass-transport losses are most severe for IJP at 0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² and USC at 0.1 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², however, for different underlying reasons. In the IJP case, increasing catalyst layer thickness leads to more compact structures with limited porosity (< 50 %, see Fig. S11), which restricts gas diffusion. In contrast, the reduction of mass-transport loss with increasing Pt loading of USC CLs can be explained by a combination of morphological and transport effects. At a very low loading (0.1 mg Pt cm⁻²), the USC forms discontinuous regions with poor percolation of both electronic, ionic and gas phases, leading to localised hindered gas transport. As the loading increases, the catalyst layer becomes more

Fig. 8. A) Cyclic voltammetry with H₂ at anode and N₂ at cathode, and B) effective platinum surface area on cathode. Testing conditions: 80 °C, 100 ml min⁻¹ N₂ at cathode, H₂ at anode, 100 % relative humidity of the feed gases.

homogeneous, resulting in better current distribution and lower local oxygen depletion. Furthermore, low Pt loaded CLs are known to suffer from increased local oxygen transport resistance inversely proportional to the electrode roughness factor ($\text{cm}_{\text{Pt}}^2 \text{cm}_{\text{CCM}}^{-2}$) [27]. IJP layers seem to suffer less from this penalty due to their superior structural properties, but this requires further investigation. Finally, thin CL are more prone to liquid flooding. As more USC layers are added, the overall structure remains relatively unchanged and their porosity remains relatively high (> 60 %, see Fig. S11), allowing the thicker catalyst layer to benefit from the increased Pt loading without significantly hindering reactant transport due to layer compaction. The observed trends require deeper electrochemical analysis to clarify how variations in charge-transfer, ion-transport, and Pt utilisation contribute to the performance reversal between IJP and USC CCMs.

A broader comparison of CCM performances reported in literature for both techniques, including the present study, is provided in SI (Table S2), highlighting the recent progress achieved through optimised CL architecture and deposition strategies. The CCMs prepared by IJP as well as USC in this work achieve peak power densities comparable to the best performing ones described in literature.

3.4.2. EIS analysis

In the context of the intriguing load curve behaviour, EIS analysis provides a deeper understanding of the factors affecting fuel cell performance by deconvoluting impedance spectra into distinct contributions of individual components and transport phenomena. Fig. 7A represents a typical Nyquist diagram of the fuel cell operated at 1 A cm⁻² and Fig. 7B and Fig. 7C show ohmic and charge transfer resistances evaluated at various current densities and Pt loadings. The total charge transfer resistance was separated into up to four contributing resistances with different time constants represented by corresponding number of Voigt elements in series [28,29]. The time constant located at $\sim 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ s is related to the hydrogen oxidation reaction. The second time constant with a value of $\sim 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s is related to ion transport in CLs. The third constant at $\sim 1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ s then corresponds to oxygen reduction reaction. The fourth time constant at $\sim 5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ s occurring in some cases is caused by diffusion of gases to the reaction site.

Quantitatively, at 1 A cm⁻² the IJP series shows ohmic resistance rising from 42.4 ± 0.4 to 59.3 ± 0.5 m Ω cm² as Pt loading increases from 0.1 to 0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², opposed to a decrease in total charge-transfer resistance from 168 ± 3 to 109 ± 1 m Ω cm². The oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) kinetic polarisation is the primary contributor and drops from 145 to 66 m Ω cm² with loading, while a low-frequency contribution becomes measurable at higher current densities (up to 8 m Ω cm²). For USC, ohmic resistance changes only slightly (from 52.6 ± 0.8 to 49.8 ± 0.3 m Ω cm² at 1 A cm⁻²) but polarisation resistance decreases

significantly (from 429 ± 10 to 103 ± 5 m Ω cm² at A cm⁻²) as the CL loading is increased, driven by a large reduction of ORR kinetic polarisation (from 313 to 69 m Ω cm² at A cm⁻²), indicating improved utilisation and structural continuity at higher loading.

IJP CCMs exhibit an increase in ohmic resistance with Pt loading, which is counterintuitive to the layer compaction. However, this could be explained by several effects: 1) The shift of the reaction area closer to the CL-GDL interface due to worsened mass transport, lengthening the pathway for proton conduction. 2) Occurrence of a skin layer with high ionomer content on the surface of each deposited layer. Multi-pass inkjet-printed layers dry each pass from the top, enriching ionomer at the air interface. Stacking many passes results in thin, ionomer-rich interlayers and a denser near-surface zone. These laminated sheets add series protonic resistance and manifest as a higher high-frequency intercept already at low current density. However, this hypothesis requires further analysis to fully confirm. Although a higher Pt content reduces the cathode charge transfer resistance (CTR) by increasing the electrochemically active surface area (ECSA), the associated increase in ohmic losses limits performance gains. This is directly impacting the performance of the cell (see Fig. 6), where the decrease of performance in activation and ohmic-controlled area of load curve for sample Inkjet 0.3 is visible. In the case of the former, decrease of voltage is related to a lower number of active sites due to ionomer phase separation between layers, while the latter is caused by increased ohmic resistance of CL.

In the detailed polarisation resistance analysis, ion transport resistance within the IJP CL increases with Pt loading. While this component remains moderate compared to other contributions, the trend suggests that the proton conduction path is extended in thicker IJP layers, likely due to a shift in the reaction zone closer to the CL-GDL interface. Furthermore, mass transport resistance increases slightly with Pt loading, especially at higher current densities. This indicates that oxygen diffusion through the catalyst layer becomes progressively hindered as the layer thickens and densifies with more printed layers. However, the total CTR remains lower compared to the USC layers due to low ORR resistance, indicating high Pt surface utilisation.

In contrast, USC CCMs exhibit an opposite trend in decreasing the ohmic resistance with increasing Pt loading. At low cathode Pt loading (0.1 mg_{Pt} cm⁻²), USC CCMs exhibit a significantly increased CTR, which is caused by poor CL homogeneity (Fig. S8G). However, as the CL becomes thicker, the CTR resistance decreases. This is because of their structural uniformity improvement, making more efficient electrochemical performance possible. Polarisation resistance analysis supports this observation, showing that the ion transport resistance is initially higher in USC compared to IJP, but decreases with higher loadings, indicating better structural continuity within the catalyst layer with additional deposited layers. Additionally, the cathode charge transfer

Table 2

Qualitative summarisation of the CCM properties and performance. Green dot – good, orange dot – normal or average, red dot – bad.

	USC 0.1	USC 0.2	USC 0.3	IJP 0.1	IJP 0.2	IJP 0.3
Homogeneity	●	●	●	●	●	●
Voltage at 0.1 A cm ⁻²	●	●	●	●	●	●
Voltage at 1 A cm ⁻²	●	●	●	●	●	●
Ohmic resistance	●	●	●	●	●	●
Polarisation resistance	●	●	●	●	●	●
ECSA	●	●	●	●	●	●

resistance remains higher for USC CCMs, particularly at low Pt loadings, reinforcing the conclusion that USC suffers from poor catalyst utilisation and inhomogeneous Pt distribution and structure for thin layers. At high Pt loadings (0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻²), the value of CTR for USC CCMs is the lowest. Together with relatively low ohmic resistance, this explains the good performance of this CL, as seen in Fig. 6.

3.4.3. Electrochemically active Pt surface area on the cathode

To further build on the observed performance and EIS trends and to address the question of Pt catalyst surface utilisation, the electrochemically active surface area of Pt catalyst on the cathode side was determined. CV under H₂ flow at the anode and N₂ at the cathode was used for this purpose. The resulting polarisation curves are shown in Fig. 8. The analysis reveals that, in general, the IJP layers exhibit significantly higher Pt utilisation compared to the USC layers. This is due to the better homogeneity of the catalyst and binder distribution in the IJP layers, which leads to greater accessibility of the Pt particles.

When considering the total Pt surface area, an increase in the active Pt surface area is observed with increasing Pt loading. However, the relationship becomes more complex when normalising the surface area with respect to the Pt loading. For the IJP samples, Pt utilisation increases from 38.7 to 52.2 m² g⁻¹ with Pt loading increasing from 0.1 to 0.2 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² and then decreases to 43.4 m² g⁻¹ at the highest loading. In contrast, the USC layers display an increasing trend of Pt utilisation with loading. For the USC with loading 0.1 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², the Pt area is very low and no H₂ adsorption peak is distinguishable. This is caused by the low connectivity of the ion conductive phase. The Pt surface area of the IJP sample with 0.2 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² is more than three times higher than for the USC sample with the same loading. At 0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² the USC layer reaches ECSA value of 25.39 m² g⁻¹, comparable to other literature [5]. This suggests that at low Pt loadings, the USC method is less efficient due to poorer CL homogeneity and less favourable inner structure that limits the number of active sites. These ECSA results are aligned with the observed impedance and load curve trends. The IJP layers show a better catalyst accessibility even at low Pt loadings, however, as Pt loadings increase the layers gradually develop transport and protonic constraints. On the other hand, the USC layers improve from a kinetically limited to a better utilised structure as the Pt loading increases. These findings are summarised in Table 2 as general trends in CL structure-performance relationship.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the successful implementation of an industrial type IJP printhead for the fabrication of high-performance CCMs for PEMFCs. By the systematic study of printing parameters, such as ink formulation, drop space, printhead distance, and the number of printed layers, it is possible to achieve a significant improvement in the layer uniformity, crack suppression, and catalyst distribution.

Increasing the distance between printhead and membrane to 24 mm

resulted in less cracks occurrence mostly due to partial drying of the drops before landing on the membrane. However, the negative consequences such as loss of the catalyst in intended area of deposition, undefined edges and poor CLs homogeneity, negate the advantage of cracks suppression. Therefore, a shorter distance of 4 mm was preferable. The most effective way to mitigate cracks was found in reducing the drop space and subsequent compensation of the Pt loading with the number of printhead paths, that facilitate drying process and improved homogeneity of the CLs. Strategy of crack mitigation was successfully applied for the CLs with varied Pt loadings (0.1–0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻²) for Nafion 212 membrane and ethanol–water based catalyst ink.

A comparison with a different fabrication technique (USC) using the same ink and testing procedure was made. CCMs prepared by USC showed a peak power density of 1.12 W cm⁻² at 0.3 mg_{Pt} cm⁻², while the IJP reached a comparable peak power density of 1.13 W cm⁻² at a lower cathode loading of 0.1 mg_{Pt} cm⁻². This is due to lower ohmic and polarisation resistance and higher electrochemically active surface area of IJP CLs, especially at lower Pt loadings, indicating a better reactant and electron transport with high Pt utilisation. This highlights superior homogeneity of IJP layers and supports the possibility of the further reduction of Pt loading, while maintaining fuel cell performance. Therefore, IJP opens a way to highly precise and versatile, high-capacity production of advanced PEMFC MEA with low Pt loadings.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

T. Zubkova: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **K. Heinrich:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **M. Hala:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **M. Prokop:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **T. Jedlicka:** Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **K. Bouzek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **A. Willert:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **R. Zichner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2025.137376>.

Data availability

Data for electrochemical test will be available 10.5281/zenodo.15236180. Other materials will be made available on request.

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